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DEVELOPMENT OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN: FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND MODERN TRENDS

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Abstract: Uzbekistan possesses substantial potential for pilgrimage tourism, owing to its rich cultural heritage, distinctive historical landmarks, and natural beauty. However, to fully harness these opportunities, it is crucial to enhance infrastructure, analyze international experiences, and incorporate modern trends. This article examines strategies for developing pilgrimage tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan, with particular emphasis on Indonesia's experience in this field, and discusses the prospects for its adaptation in the local context. Foreign practices and contemporary approaches are thoroughly analyzed.

Key words: tourism, pilgrimage tourism, Islamic tourism, services, tourist market, tourists, pilgrimage.

INTRODUCTION

Pilgrimage tourism refers to the travel undertaken by individuals for religious purposes. While it is traditionally associated with spiritual journeys, it can also encompass secular travel that holds personal or cultural significance for the traveler. Pilgrimage tourism plays a vital role in the economic, cultural, and social development of many countries around the world.

Uzbekistan is renowned for its ancient cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, each notable for its unique architecture and rich historical heritage. Despite this, certain infrastructural challenges persist, particularly in the areas of transportation, hospitality services, and the accessibility of pilgrimage sites. Consequently, it is essential to develop the country's pilgrimage tourism infrastructure by examining international experiences and integrating modern approaches.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The scientific article "Halal Tourism: Essence, Factors, and Modern Development Trends" by A.Yu. Aleksandrova [1], along with "Halal Tourism in the Modern World" by M.V. Umanskaya and Z.I. Davlatova [2], provides an in-depth analysis of the concept of halal tourism and its key components. These studies explore the nature of halal tourism, the factors influencing its development, and contemporary trends shaping the industry.

Uzbek researchers have also contributed significantly to the study of halal tourism. For instance, A. Asadov, in his work "The Experience of Implementing Halal Tourism Standards in Non-Muslim Countries" [3], examines the integration of halal standards outside the Islamic world. U. Barotov's article "Analysis of Leading Online Travel Agencies in Halal Tourism and Their Prospects in Our Country" [4] investigates the role of digital platforms in promoting halal tourism. Similarly, U. Turdiyeva's study "The Impact of Halal Products and Services on the Tourism Industry" [5] analyzes how halal-certified offerings influence the broader tourism sector.

Despite the growing body of literature, much of the research remains focused on conceptual and geographical dimensions, with relatively limited attention paid to the economic aspects of halal and pilgrimage tourism. Notably, issues such as the dynamics of international tourism services, the development of the tourism sector, state policy directions, and the creation of a favorable tourism environment are only partially addressed in economic studies.

Moreover, analyzing global experiences in pilgrimage tourism services and assessing their practical implementation, as well as thoroughly evaluating the effectiveness of government policies in this field, remain critical areas for further scholarly investigation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research process utilized scientific methods such as observation, comparison, systematic and comparative analysis, and statistical grouping. Numerous national and foreign sources on the topic were studied and thoroughly analyzed. Modern trends related to the topic were evaluated, and analytical work was conducted based on statistical data. Additionally, the current state and development prospects of infrastructure in Uzbekistan were analyzed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Among Southeast Asian countries, Indonesia and Malaysia are leaders in pilgrimage tourism. Indonesia is located in the southeastern part of Asia and ranks 14th in the world in terms of territory. As of 2024, its population exceeds 279.7 million, making it one of the top 10 most populous countries in the world. Tourism is one of Indonesia's important economic sectors and a major source of income for the country's economy. Between 2010–2019, the number of tourists visiting Indonesia steadily increased. In 2010, the number of tourists exceeded 7 million, while in 2019, this figure reached 16.1 million, representing a 130% increase. However, the COVID-19 pandemic caused a sharp decline in the international tourism market. As a result, in 2020, the number of tourists visiting Indonesia was only 4 million, a 42% decrease compared to 2019. In 2021, the number of tourists further decreased by 62.5%, dropping to 1.5 million. The main reason for this decline was the prolonged pandemic-related restrictions.

In 2022, the number of tourists visiting Indonesia exceeded 5.8 million, and in 2023, this figure reached 11.68 million, representing a 98.3% increase in one year. In 2024, Indonesia welcomed 13.9 million foreign tourists, showing a significant increase from the 11.68 million tourists recorded in 2023. The data indicates that Indonesia's tourism industry is growing significantly each year. To ensure sustainable growth in tourism, the country focuses on several key principles. Indonesia consists of 17,100 islands and is distinguished by its beautiful natural landscapes and great tourism potential. As the country with the largest Muslim population in the world, it continuously develops pilgrimage tourism. The development of halal tourism in the country has a positive impact not only on Muslim tourists but also on tourists of other religions. Halal tourism provides open and comfortable conditions for everyone. This type of tourism has made Indonesia a friendly destination for Muslim tourists worldwide. To achieve this, standardization and the introduction of clear halal tourism standards were required. The unique feature of pilgrimage tourism is that it requires tourist destinations, hotels, restaurants, and resorts to comply with "halal" standards, which ensures high-quality and comfortable services not only for Muslims but for all tourists.

In Indonesia, tourism is organized based on principles such as sustainability, preserving cultural heritage, protecting ecological balance, and creating comfortable conditions for Muslim tourists. These principles define the country's main directions in tourism development and aim to make tourism activities long-term, socio-economically beneficial, and environmentally safe. Below are the main principles of tourism in Indonesia: Sustainable tourism: Indonesia adheres to the principle of sustainability in tourism development. This includes nature conservation, considering local communities' interests, and long-term development. Preserving and promoting cultural heritage: This involves preserving cultural landmarks such as Borobudur and Prambanan, and promoting traditional culture through dances, music, crafts, and national dishes. Developing halal tourism: This includes providing halal-certified meals, prayer facilities in public spaces, and gender-based comfort such as separate swimming pools and spa centers. Ecotourism: Indonesia protects national parks, reserves, and marine ecosystems while promoting nature-friendly tourism activities. Using innovations and technologies: Smart tourism solutions such as mobile apps, virtual reality (VR), and artificial intelligence (AI), as well as online platforms for promotion and booking, are prioritized. International cooperation and tourism promotion: Through global campaigns like "Wonderful Indonesia" and simplified visa regulations, the country strengthens its international tourism appeal.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Halal tourism in Indonesia is well-organized as a separate sector of the national economy and has significant economic potential. Halal tourism is intended not only for a specific segment of the population but for all tourists. The main principle of pilgrimage tourism in the country is strict adherence to standards in tourism management and caring for all tourists and the environment. Developing pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan and

making rational use of tourism resources and potential will positively impact the country's external economic activities, increase foreign currency earnings, improve the export structure, and diversify it. By generalizing Indonesia's experience, it is advisable to develop pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan in the following directions: expanding international relations in tourism by developing cooperation with geographically close countries and developing a comprehensive system of measures to attract foreign investments in tourism; modernizing tourism infrastructure through building new hotels, campsites, motels, and hostels, as well as renovating existing ones, introducing "halal" standards and creating a material-technical base that meets international requirements; ensuring convenience by organizing prayer rooms and rest areas in airports, railway stations, and bus stations; developing information and communication systems by introducing modern information systems in tourist reception centers; and providing information support for the tourism sector by using the latest technologies in the tourism business and promoting the country's tourism potential on the international tourism market through the internet. Using Indonesia's experience, developing pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan will not only stimulate the country's economy but also enhance its international reputation.

References:

1. Aleksandrova, A. Yu. Halal Tourism: Essence, Factors, and Modern Development Trends in the World. *Priority Directions and Problems of Development of Domestic and International Tourism in Russia* (2018): 3–9.
2. Asadov, N. The Experience of Implementing Halal Tourism Standards in Non-Muslim Countries. *Interpretation and Research* 1.1 (2023).
3. Turdiyeva, U. The Impact of Halal Products and Services on the Tourism Industry. *Applied Sciences in the Modern World: Problems and Solutions* 1.23 (2022): 52–55.
4. Umanskaya, M. V., & Davlatova, Z. I. Halal Tourism in the Modern World (2021): 106–113.
5. Barotov, U. Analysis of Leading Online Travel Agencies in Halal Tourism and Their Prospects in Our Country. Center for Scientific Publications (buxdu.uz) 46.46 (2024).
6. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-6600413#-6605156>
7. <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/indicator/indonesia/visitor-arrivals>
8. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/3d55e868-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/3d55e868-en>
9. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1150613/indonesia-tourism-gdp-direct-contribution-share/>
10. <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/journal>

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